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Microscale testing and modelling for damage tolerant composite materials and structures

41st Risø International Symposium on Materials Science, 7-10 September 2020

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1. Background and motivation

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Background and motivation

Society

- Composites based on long aligned fibres are increasingly used in large load-carrying structures subjected to cyclic loading
 - Examples: Wind turbine rotor blades, boats and bridges
 - The trend is towards yet larger size – but big structures cannot be made free of defects... but are expensive to discard
- ⇒ Need for more damage tolerant materials and design approaches for structures

Scientific challenges

- Composites are multi-scale
 - Fatigue damage evolution is complicated (progressive damage evolution)
- ⇒ Prediction of damage evolution under cyclic loading is difficult

Background and motivation - purpose

Purpose of present work

- Go toward design approaches beyond “no damage growth” design criteria
- The damage evolution of composites should be predicable from properties of fibre, matrix and the fibre/matrix interface as microstructure geometry
- Present ideas on how damage tolerant material behaviour and structures can be developed for fibre composites
- Illustrate ideas by two cases
 - in-plane fatigue of unidirectional composites
 - delamination fatigue crack grow at ply-drops

2. Concepts of damage tolerance

1. Background and motivation
2. Concepts of damage tolerance
3. Fatigue damage mechanism maps
4. Model of in-plane fatigue
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Concepts of damage tolerance – in aerospace

Damage tolerance concepts in aerospace

- Damage growth in the form of cyclic crack growth is allowed
- Crack growth rate in structures are predicted using Paris-Erdogan law – parameters obtained independently from Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics test specimens
- Structures are regularly inspected for cracks by NDT (non-destructive testing) methods
- Inspection intervals are set such that the largest un-detected crack cannot grow to critical size before next inspection

Concepts of damage tolerance – more general

What is “damage tolerance”?

- A structures ability to undergo distributed and localized damage (crack growth) without failing
- The first mode of damage must not lead to imminent failure
- Damage should growth in a stable manner
- Damage should be detectable and predictable (so that there is plenty of time to reach – inspect, repair, replace)

Damage tolerance as a combined materials and structure property

$$\sigma_n = \sigma_n(\delta_n, \delta_t) \quad \tau_s = \tau_s(\delta_n, \delta_t)$$

What controls stability of crack growth?

- Focus on crack bridging of a crack
- Assume that bridging tractions can be derived from a potential function

Criterion for stable crack growth:

$$J_{ext} = J_R \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dJ_{ext}}{dl} \leq \sigma_n^* \frac{\partial \delta_n^*}{\partial l} + \tau_s^* \frac{\partial \delta_t^*}{\partial l}$$

Damage tolerance as a combined materials and structure property

$$\sigma_n = \sigma_n(\delta_n, \delta_t) \quad \tau_s = \tau_s(\delta_n, \delta_t)$$

Bridging Stresses

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Depends on structural geometry and dimensions

Cohesive traction at end of bridging zone

Openings at end of bridging zone

Damage tolerance as a combined materials and structure property

Crack growth stability is inherently a coupled **materials-structure** property

$$\sigma_n = \sigma_n(\delta_n, \delta_t) \quad \tau_s = \tau_s(\delta_n, \delta_t)$$

What controls stable crack growth

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↑
Depends on structural geometry and dimensions

Cohesive traction at end of bridging zone

↑
Openings at end of bridging zone

3. Model of in-plane fatigue

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In-plane fatigue - Fatigue damage mechanisms map

In-plane fatigue - Fatigue damage mechanisms map

Mechanism I: Fibre failure with progressive debonding

Figure 11 Debond growth from a single fibre break in Region III in CF/epoxy ($\epsilon = 0.89\%$).

Figure 12 Debond propagation from a single fibre break in Region III in CF/epoxy ($\epsilon = 0.89\%$).

In-plane fatigue – Prediction of a fatigue limit

Microscale parameters:
obtained from microscale
experiments

[Sørensen and Goutianos, Mechanics of Materials, (2019)]

In-plane fatigue - Fatigue damage mechanisms map

Mechanism II: Growth of clusters of broken fibres

Note: Not "random" fibre failures...

Mechanism:

Progressive failure of neighbour fibres at damage front

Damage zone size

[Jespersen and Mikkelsen, Comp. Sci. Techn., 2017]

Mechanism II: Growth of clusters of broken fibres

[Goutianos and Peijs, Adv. Comp. Lett., 2001]

... the debond crack growth increase but arrests after a number of cycles...

Mechanism II: Growth of clusters of broken fibres

[Goutianos and Peijs, Adv. Comp. Lett., 2001]

... the debond crack growth increase but arrests after a number of cycles...

Mechanism II: Growth of clusters of broken fibres

Progressive debonding and failure of neighbour fibre:

- Decrease in interfacial friction shear stress, τ_s
- Debond crack tip stress field thrown onto neighbour fibres

Mechanism II: Growth of clusters of broken fibres

Prediction of damage growth rate (mechanisms II):

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{3}\pi}{2V_f} \frac{r}{\mathcal{N}^*}}$$

where \mathcal{N}^* is the number of cycles it takes to break one row of neighbour fibres.

\mathcal{N}^* depends on several microscale parameters – no detailed here.

[Sørensen et al., Comp. Sci. Techn. 2020, submitted]

Microscale parameters

Microscale parameter (mechanisms II):

E_f	Young's modulus of the fibre	Fibre
α_f	Thermal expansion coefficient of the fibres	
r	Fibre radius	
$\sigma_0(L_0)$	Characteristic strength (Weibull model)	
m	Weibull modulus (Weibull model)	
L_0	Reference length (Weibull model)	
E_m	Young's modulus of the matrix	Matrix
α_m	Thermal expansion coefficient of the matrix	
\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^m	Mode I fracture energy of matrix	
\mathcal{G}_{IIc}^m	Mode II fracture energy of matrix	
\mathcal{G}_c^i	Interface fracture energy (debond energy)	Interface
τ_s	Interfacial frictional sliding shear stress	

Mechanism II: Growth of clusters of broken fibres

Prediction of damage growth rate (mechanisms II):

Effects of Weibull modulus, m on damage growth rate da/dN

Mechanism III: Splitting along fibres

[Jespersen and Mikkelsen, Comp. Sci. Techn., 2017]

Mechanism:
Splitting along fibres at damage front

[Korkiakoski et al., Int. J. Fatigue, 2016]

Mechanism III: Splitting along fibres

Prediction of fatigue life (Mechanisms III):

$$N_f = \frac{g_s}{da/dN}$$

$$g_s = \frac{4G_{IIc}^c}{E_c \bar{\epsilon}_{max}^2}$$

[Sørensen, Comp. Sci. Techn. 2019]

Mechanism III: Splitting along fibres

Prediction of fatigue life, S-N diagram (Mechanism III):

Effects of Weibull modulus, m
on fatigue life N_f

Mechanism III: Splitting along fibres

Prediction of fatigue life, S-N diagram (Mechanism III):

Effects of fibre volume fraction, V_f on fatigue life N_f

S_N_Predictions_242_246_1f.opj

[Sørensen et al., Comp. Sci. Techn. 2020, submitted]

4. Model of delamination fatigue from ply-drops

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Delamination crack growth from ply-drops

Delaminations from a ply drop:

Ply-drop with a defect

Fatigue delamination crack growth from ply-drops

[Courtesy of dr. Stergios Goutianos]

An example: Delamination from a ply-drop

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An example: Delamination from a ply-drop

An example: Delamination from a ply-crack

... delamination A grows with a constant rate...

Note: Some cracks stop growing!

Delamination from ply-drops - Fatigue damage mechanisms map

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops

Delaminations from two ply drops:

Ply-drop A

Ply-drop B

What controls which delamination propagates fastest during cyclic loading?

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops

Delamination model of tri-layer:

- laminate with 3 lamina

Model with no shear stress along interface ($\tau_s = 0$):

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops

Cyclic crack growth:

- Paris-Erdogan law

$$\frac{d\ell}{dN} = C (\Delta K - (\Delta K)_{th})^{\tilde{m}}$$

Model prediction for no shear stress along interface ($\tau_s = 0$):

- selected parameters

$$(d\ell/dN)|_B / (d\ell/dN)|_A \approx 0.25$$

$$(d\ell/dN)|_C / (d\ell/dN)|_A \approx 1.4$$

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops

Predictions:

- Delamination B grows slower than Delamination A
- Once grown past crack tip B, Delamination A speeds up

Cyclic crack growth:

- Paris-Erdogan law

$$\frac{d\ell}{dN} = C (\Delta K - (\Delta K)_{th})^{\tilde{m}}$$

Model prediction for no shear stress along interface ($\tau_s = 0$):

- selected parameters

$$(d\ell/dN)|_B / (d\ell/dN)|_A \approx 0.25$$

$$(d\ell/dN)|_C / (d\ell/dN)|_A \approx 1.4$$

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops

Design against fast crack growth:

- Number of cycles for Crack Tip A to catch Crack Tip B (if they start growing at the same time):

$$N_c = \frac{L}{(d\ell/dN)|_A - (d\ell/dN)|_B}$$

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops – with fibre bridging

Fibres being peeled-off parallel to the fibre direction:

- Constant stress acts as a shear stress along the bridging zone

$$\tau_s = \left[\frac{2\mathcal{G}_c^i}{E_f r} \right]^{1/2} \tilde{\eta} \pi r^2 E_f$$

Monotonic opening:

a)

Cyclic opening/closure:

b)

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops – with fibre bridging

Relation between max stress and debond length A:

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{max}}{E_2} = \frac{(1 + 2\Sigma\eta)}{\Sigma\eta} \frac{\tau_s}{E_2} \frac{\ell_d}{h_2} + \sqrt{\frac{2(1 + 2\Sigma\eta)}{\Sigma\eta} \frac{J_{max}}{E_2 h_2}}$$

Debond length that gives $J_{max} = 0$:

$$\frac{\ell_d^a}{h_2} = \frac{\Sigma\eta}{(1 + 2\Sigma\eta)} \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{max}}{\tau_s}$$

$$\Sigma = \frac{E_1}{E_2} \quad \text{and} \quad \eta = \frac{h_1}{h_2}$$

Delamination crack growth from ply-drops – with fibre bridging

Relation between max stress and debond length A:

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{max}}{E_2} = \frac{(1 + 2\Sigma\eta)}{\Sigma\eta} \frac{\tau_s}{E_2} \frac{\ell_d}{h_2} + \sqrt{\frac{2(1 + 2\Sigma\eta)}{\Sigma\eta} \frac{J_{max}}{E_2 h_2}}$$

Debond length that gives $J_{max} = 0$:

$$\frac{\ell_d^a}{h_2} = \frac{\Sigma\eta}{(1 + 2\Sigma\eta)} \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{max}}{\tau_s}$$

$$\Sigma = \frac{E_1}{E_2} \quad \text{and} \quad \eta = \frac{h_1}{h_2}$$

Criterion for crack arrest:

$$\ell_d^a < L$$

The debond length A will thus arrest at length ℓ_d^a

5. Measurement of microscale parameters

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Microscale parameters

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Measurement of microscale parameters

Fibre properties

- Stiffness and strength properties can be measured by single fibre tensile testing
- Now, commercial automatized single fibre testing equipment is available \Rightarrow large number of fibres can be tested reproducibly
- Issue: Relevant length in composites smaller than measured gauge length

Matrix properties

- Matrix materials can be characterized as bulk materials
- Issues with constraint curing (spacing between fibres about 1 micron)
- On microscale: triaxial stress state \Rightarrow limit yielding?

Measurement of microscale parameters

Interface properties

- No interface test method is perfect
 - microbond tests: evaporation from large surface?
 - single fibre fragmentation tests: embedded fibre must fail first
 - pull-out: small displacement difficult to measure
 - push-out: surface preparation (polishing) can induce debonding
- Concepts for characterisation:
 - shear strength?
 - debonding energy (breakage of chemical bonds)
 - frictional sliding shear stress (slip along debonded interface)

Measurement of microscale parameters

Interface characterisation

- Debonding is bi-material fracture
 - expect strong mode mixity effects

- Peel off: $\psi \approx 30$ degrees

[Thouless and Jensen, 1992]

[Liechti and Chai, 1992]

Measurement of microscale parameters

Interface characterisation

- Frictional sliding shear stress:

$$\tau_s = \tau_s^0 - \mu \sigma_{rr} \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma_{rr} < 0$$

Effect of roughness

Coulomb friction coefficient

Stress normal to interface (depends e.g. on $\Delta a \Delta T$)

- How to characterize cyclic slip (wear of roughness asperities)?
 - decreasing τ_s^0 ...or decreasing μ ?

6. Summary

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6. Summary

- Damage tolerant behaviour is increasingly needed for large composite structures made in very large sizes
- Crack growth stability is inherently a combined material-structure property
- Micromechanical modelling can help guide the processing of more damage tolerant materials
- Mechanical characterisation of fibre/matrix interface remains a challenge

Thanks for your attention!

Any questions?

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Fatigue damage mechanisms map

Purpose:

- Experimentally, identify microscale damage mechanisms as a function of number of load cycles for various maximum cyclic strain levels
- Visualize the dominant damage mechanisms
- Construct micromechanical models of each damage mechanism
- Link the micromechanical models together
- Explore by modelling how each mechanism can be slowed or arrested

Remarks:

The concept of fatigue damage mechanisms maps is applicable on materials and generic components (elements) scale

Concepts of damage tolerance – in general

What is meant by “stable manner”?

- Under static loading, “stable manner” means that damage growth must arrest under fixed load and a higher applied load is required to develop further damage
- Under cyclic loading, “stable manner” means that fatigue damage should evolve slowly, i.e., under many load cycles

Concepts of damage tolerance – in general

What is meant by “damage being detectable”?

- Distributed damages should result in measureable changes in materials stiffnesses (“damage indicators”), e.g. by strain gauges, fibre optics sensors or acoustic emission sensors, etc.
- Damages should be detectable by non-destructive methods (ultrasound scanning, thermography)
- Preferably, we should be able to identify the damage type, its physical location, shape, size and depth

Concepts of damage tolerance – in general

What is meant by “damage being predicable”?

- The damage evolution and load carrying capability of the structure can be predicted static loading
- The damage growth rate and remaining number of load cycles can be predicted for cyclic loading
- Predictions should be made using models where the relevant mechanical properties are determined by independent experiments

Concepts of damage tolerance – in general

What is meant by “damage control” materials?

- Materials, that has been tailor-made such that progressive damage evolution behaves in a pre-determined damage tolerant manner

Taylor-making of materials:

- materials and component testing to identify damage types
- micromechanical modelling to find the best microscale parameters
- Iterations of:
 - Microscale experiments to characterize current microscale mechanical properties
 - Change in processing conditions toward “optimal” conditions

Fatigue damage mechanisms map

- Example 2: Delamination from ply-drops

Frictional sliding stress decay and debond length

